

THE BASIS OF PURITY-KINDNESS-CONSEQUENCE OF RELATIONSHIPS IN THE FAMILY AND ITS ROLE IN YOUTH DEVELOPMENT

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***Annotatsiya:** In this article, attention to family, manners, and education is a duty embedded in our blood. It was stated that family education has a deep impact on the mental world, emotions and feelings of children compared to social education, and it is necessary to be able to maintain the norm in giving love.*

***Key words:** Family, youth, love, consequences, education, science, education, sustainable development.*

ОСНОВА ЧИСТОТЫ-ДОБРОТЫ-СЛЕДСТВИЕ ОТНОШЕНИЙ В СЕМЬЕ И ЕЕ РОЛЬ В РАЗВИТИИ МОЛОДЕЖИ

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***Аннотация:** В этой статье внимание к семье, манерам и образованию является долгом, заложенным в нашей крови. Констатировано, что семейное воспитание оказывает глубокое воздействие на психический мир, эмоции и чувства детей по сравнению с социальным воспитанием, и необходимо уметь поддерживать норму в проявлении любви.*

***Ключевые слова:** Семья, молодежь, любовь, последствия, образование, наука, образование, устойчивое развитие.*

OILADA MUNOSABATLARNING POKLIGI-MEHR-OQIBATLILIK ASOSI VA UNING YOSHLAR KAMOLOTIDA TUTGAN O'RNI

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***Annotatsiya:** Ushbu maqolada oila, o'qib-axloq va ta'lim-tarbiyaga e'tibor qon-qonimizga singib ketgan burch ekanligi. Oilaviy tarbiya ijtimoiy tarbiyaga nisbatan bolalarning ruhiy olamiga, hissiyoti va tuyg'ulariga chuqur ta'sir ko'rsatishi hamda mehr-muhabbat berishda ham me'yorni saqlay bilish kerakligi bayon qilingan.*

***Tayanch so'zlar:** Oila, yoshlar, mehr, oqibat, ta'lim, fan, tarbiya, barqaror taraqqiyot.*

The backbone of the family. In the minds of our children, feelings of love for the country and the Motherland are formed in the family, in the neighborhood where they live. The country's future, peace and prosperity depends first of all on our children growing up in this small community. As long as education is well organized in any family and neighborhood, that family and neighborhood will flourish. Many people think about the question of when to start raising a child. Many scientists have given different answers to it. In particular, Ibn Sina answered that it is necessary to deal with the education of a child before its birth, starting from the mother's womb.

Paying attention to family, morals and education is one of our duties that is ingrained in our blood. The proverb "One child has seven neighboring parents" is typical of our people. This proverb itself shows how important it is for us to raise children and take care of the family. The residents of the neighborhood, especially the elderly, never passed by a child doing a dirty job on the street, and immediately reprimanded him and called him to the right path. After all, our holy religion, which commands to be beautiful, polite, and well-behaved in every way, and to purify the soul, attaches great importance to the family. The atmosphere in the family becomes stable when parents feel their responsibilities. In order for children to grow up politely, together with their parents, the neighborhood is a great example school. It is not for nothing that our people say that "birds do what they see in their nests". A parent raising a child should be able to show noble qualities in every movement, posture, behavior, and interaction with others. Because the child is extremely imitative and observant by nature. That is why those around him influence them with their habits, sometimes without realizing it. Rough relationships in the family, a lot of lying, and unpleasant behavior create an unhealthy environment that negatively affects the child's upbringing. If a child grows up hearing harsh words from his parents and being beaten, this will have a negative effect on his character. And this, in turn, creates "spiritually sick" people from children raised in an unhealthy environment in the family. They also have a negative impact on the morale of the society. In the family, parents are influenced by "mass culture", which has a negative impact on children's upbringing. Thanks to independence, our people are visiting foreign countries and returning as witnesses of new people and traditions. Including our citizens who travel to European countries today, among Western teenagers, the level of organized crime and violence is higher than among the youth of other countries. The reason for this is that children are given more freedom than before. They are saying that no one will stop them from now indulging in lust and indulging in various immoral actions.

During his life, a person considers a person as an example, from which a person aspires to live like him, to achieve the same success as he has achieved, to reach great heights. Today, the fact that young members of society take the thinking and lifestyle

of other cultures as an example for their lives causes many problems. In the 21st century, different lifestyles and ideas have come into competition. In order to achieve success in this, each country should have an ideology that is based on communicating its religious and national values to others while preserving its identity. Otherwise, losing one's identity and renouncing precious values separates a person from development and turns him into a subordinate, a man without an independent mind. It can be felt that the conspiracies that are being carried out for the realization of malicious goals are aimed at losing the identity of some nations. In this case, the focus is not on occupying the territories, but on occupying the human mind. Of course, raising a child is very complicated and responsible. This requires every parent to regularly work on himself, to be aware of all the information related to the education of children. Child rearing is not just experience, simple instructions and a collection of knowledge, but it is a complex process that includes knowledge in the fields of religious and moral knowledge, medicine, ethics, psychology, pedagogy. Today, the difficulty of family upbringing is that, firstly, as the society progresses, the demands of forming a mature person in all respects are increasing. This puts a demand to increase the quality and scope of aesthetic, sexual and moral education for the child in the family. Rasulullah (pbuh) said: "If one of you teaches your children to discipline, it is better than giving alms every day." Teaching children to discipline is the basis of family strength. In this sense, Islam encourages parents to give their children a healthy upbringing.

It is stated in the hadith that "Respect your children and treat them well." In the process of raising a child, it is required that the rights of the child are not discriminated against. Compared to social education, family education has a profound effect on children's mental world, emotions and feelings. It is necessary to be able to maintain the standard in giving love. doing everything the child says, approving all the wrong actions, or even staying silent will cause the child to grow up without education at all. Excessive caressing and caressing makes the child weak in every way, and showing affection encourages him to be more active. A grown-up boy grows up to be irresponsible, looking only for his personal interests. Therefore, the service of the mother is very necessary and important for the child to become a complete person. During childhood, the child's heart is very soft and susceptible to influence. Therefore, in religious teachings, special attention is paid to caressing children with love and making the child's childhood happy. Especially, taking into account that the heart of a girl child is sensitive, it is called to show them special affection. In religious teachings, it is considered one of the most important duties of parents to educate their children. About this, Muhammad (peace be upon him): "Educate your children, because they were born for a time that is not yours," and called every parent not to be indifferent to

the science and education of their children. The most important tool in education is to educate with kindness and sweetness. These two tools form a child. Including, it is better not to carry out education with anger and punishment. After all, forced education quickly fades from a child's memory. As a result, his interest in this field may fade. It can be seen that the beginning of education begins with good education. In the teachings of Islam, it is very important for the young generation to grow up physically healthy and strong. Our Prophet (pbuh) said about this: "Teach your children to swim and shoot a bow, and teach your girls to spin yarn." attacks on mobile phones and social networks are on the rise. While these modern means of communication are important means of communication, they have a negative effect on some spiritually immature young people. Parents and educational institutions should explain the true nature of communication tools to young people who are under the influence of social networks. Negative influence from outside education is the biggest danger. Because when a child is not allowed to have freedom in this regard in the family, he starts looking outside for reasons that satisfy his interests and motivations. Therefore, it is necessary for parents to pay great attention to the external life of their child. That is, they should control where their child goes and what they do after school or college. It is the duty of parents to create conditions for their child to learn.

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